

Synthesis, characterization and reactivity of tin(II) 2,4-dinitrophenoxide

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Abstract : Compound of composition $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ (where dnp : anion of 2,4-dinitrophenol i.e. $^-\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-2,4}$) has been synthesized by reacting anhydrous stannous chloride with 2,4-dinitrophenol in the presence of diethylamine in predetermined molar ratios (1 : 2 : 2) in tetrahydrofuran and characterized by elemental analysis, conductance, IR, ^1H NMR and TGA studies. Reaction of $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ with HgCl_2 has been investigated using potentiometric and cyclic voltammetric techniques. Double phenoxide of composition $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_4]$ has been synthesized by reacting $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ with bimolar amount of sodium salt of 2,4-dinitrophenol. Reaction of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_4]$ with anhydrous nickel chloride yields $\text{Ni}[\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_4]$. Addition compounds of composition $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ and $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2 \cdot \text{B}$ (where L = diethylamine, triethylamine and pyridine and B = 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl) have also been isolated and characterized by physico-chemical and IR spectral studies.

Keywords : Tin(II) complexes, dinitrophenoxide, addition compounds.

Chemistry of tin has been the subject of much research not only because of its fundamental properties but also due to the ever increasing catalytic, biological and industrial applications¹. The outstanding feature of the chemistry of tin(II) compounds getting easily oxidized to tin(IV) has been successfully exploited as reducing agents in inorganic, analytical and organic chemistry². Apart from this, a number of tin(II) and tin(IV) aryloxides have also been characterized as mono and dinuclear on the basis of steric bulk of the ring substituents³. Encouraged by these reports, it is considered worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of tin(II) 2,4-dinitrophenoxide and thereby investigate its physico-chemical properties.

Results and discussion

The formation of tin(II) 2,4-dinitrophenoxide has been rationalized in terms of the following reaction :

The stoichiometric composition of the solid compound isolated from the solution has been established by elemental analysis (% found (calcd.) Sn = 24.28 (24.51); C = 14.81(14.84); H = 0.59 (0.61)). The solid is greenish in colour, thermally stable, having decomposition temperature around 110 °C. It is sparingly soluble in

nitrobenzene, methanol and DMSO. The molar conductance value of the millimolar solution of this compound in nitrobenzene has been found to be too low ($1.8 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) to be assigned to 1 : 1 electrolyte. It is interesting to mention here that although the compound has been isolated from the THF solution, yet the compound appears to polymerize in the solid state, as it does not redissolve in common organic solvent completely. Molecular weight determination of this compound could not be carried out because of the insoluble nature of the solid compound in any solvent suitable for cryoscopy.

In the ^1H NMR spectra of the $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$, no signal at δ 4.6 ppm attributed to phenolic -OH proton of 2,4-dinitrophenol (dnpH) has been observed, suggesting thereby the removal of this proton during the course of the reaction. Further, the signals due to ring protons observed at 9.1, 8.5 and 7.35 ppm in pure dnpH have been found to experience a significant upfield shift and appear at 8.75, 8.05 and 6.91 ppm respectively. The upfield shift may be attributed to increased shielding of ring protons due to the participation of stereoactive lone pair of electron on tin(II) through phenolic oxygen.

A broad band observed at $\sim 3200 \text{cm}^{-1}$ due to the intramolecular hydrogen bonded phenolic -OH group in dnpH has been found to be missing in $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$. The bands observed in $3100\text{--}2900 \text{cm}^{-1}$ region assigned to $\nu(\text{CH})$ modes have remained almost unaltered while the

bands in the region 1600–1400 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ mode in the phenolic ring have been found to suffer a slight shift to higher wavenumbers possibly due to increased ring conjugation brought about by complexation.

Interestingly, most important and diagnostic band due to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ ring mode reported to occur in the region 1260–1180 cm^{-1} ⁴ and 1300–1200 cm^{-1} ⁵ in free phenols, has appeared at 1262 cm^{-1} in dnpH. In $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$, in contrast to the expected lowering in $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ mode on complexation, it has been found to remain almost unchanged. This may be due to the participation of stereo active lone pair of electron on tin(II), in line with NMR spectral observation. The coordination from oxygen of the phenol to the tin metal in the complex under study has been indicated by the appearance of entirely new bands (not present in the ligand) in the region 520–480 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{O})$ mode.

A careful examination of the thermogram of parent complex (Fig. 1) reveals that the compound is stable up to 99.1 °C, after which it appears to decompose in three stages. On the basis of weight losses, the probable

Fig. 1. TGA and DTA curves of $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2-2,4)_2$: (—) TGA, (---) DTA.

formation of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_3\text{N}_3\text{O}_7\text{Sn}$ and $\text{SnO}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ as intermediates may be proposed. The overall loss amounting to 69% corresponds to the formation of SnO_2 as an ultimate decomposition product and supports the stoichiometric composition of $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$. The decomposition scheme is shown below :

The decompositions in TG are supplemented by exothermic peaks at 236.6 °C and 686.7 °C in DTA curve.

Double phenoxides : In order to explore the possibility of formation of double phenoxide, conductometric titration between $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ versus sodium salt of 2,4-dinitrophenol (Nadnp) has been carried out. The conductance composition curve shown as graph in (Fig. 2) shows break, at $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$: Nadnp (1 : 2) molar ratio; thus indicating

Fig. 2. Conductometric titration of $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ vs Nadnp.

the formation of double phenoxide at this molar ratio. Evidenced from conductance study, compound of composition $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2-2,4)_4]$ has actually been isolated in separate experiment by reacting the known amount of tin(II) dinitrophenoxide with bimolar amount of alkali metal dinitrophenoxide in methanol under reflux. The reaction leading to the formation of desired compound may be represented as follows :

The complex is bright yellow coloured solid. Molar conductance value of millimolar solutions of this compound in nitrobenzene ($7-8 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggests that it is ionic in nature. The reaction of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2-2,4)_4]$ with anhydrous nickel chloride in equimolar ratio in methanol results into an immediate separation of quantitative amount of sodium chloride. The formation of the resulting compound can be rationalized in terms of following reaction :

Stoichiometric composition of isolated complex was established by metal analysis using atomic absorption

spectrometer (% found (calcd.) Sn = 13.07 (13.15); Ni = 6.48 (6.52)).

Reaction of tin(II)-dinitrophenoxide with HgCl₂: In view of reports in literature concerning the well-known redox reaction of stannous chloride with mercuric chloride represented below :

it is quite interesting to undertake the reaction of Sn(dnp)₂ with mercuric chloride⁶. In order to explore the possibility of such reaction, potentiometric titration has been carried out between tin(II)-dinitrophenoxide and HgCl₂ in methanol. Potential-composition curve shown as graph in (Fig. 3) shows a break at 1 : 2 (Sn(dnp)₂/HgCl₂) molar ratio. It is on the basis of this preliminary potentiometric study that a separate experiment was carried out to isolate

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titration of Sn(dnp)₂ vs HgCl₂.

the compound by reacting a known amount of Sn(dnp)₂ in methanol with bimolar amount of HgCl₂ dissolved in same solvent. During the course of reaction, greyish compound, identified as Hg₂Cl₂ was quantitatively separated out. Elemental analysis of the compound isolated as solid from the solution ((% found (calcd.) Sn = 21.66 (21.40); Cl = 12.76 (12.81)) corresponds well with its stoichiometric formulation as SnCl₂(OC₆H₃(NO₂)₂-2,4)₂ in accordance with the following reaction :

The feasibility of the above reaction is further substantiated by cyclic voltammetric studies. Unlike the reversible reaction between SnCl₂ and HgCl₂ displaying both oxidation peak and reduction peak in its voltammogram (Fig. 4(a)), the reaction of parent complex Sn(dnp)₂ and

HgCl₂ shows only the oxidation peak in the cyclic voltammogram (Fig. 4(b)) thus suggesting the

Fig. 4(a). Cyclic voltammogram of SnCl₂ vs HgCl₂.

irreversibility of the reaction. In other words, Sn^{II} has been oxidized to Sn^{IV} resulting in formation of SnCl₂(dnp)₂ but Sn^{IV} does not get reduced to Sn^{II}. This irreversibility has been attributed to extra stability of hexa-coordinated chelated Sn^{IV} complex compared to four coordinated chelated Sn^{II} complex.

Reactions with nitrogenous bases : Reactivity of the

Fig. 4(b). Cyclic voltammogram of Sn(dnp)₂ vs HgCl₂.

newly synthesized $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ has been further investigated by undertaking its reactions with various nitrogenous bases. The interaction of $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ with bimolar amounts of the bases diethylamine, triethylamine and pyridine (L) have afforded the formation of the compounds of composition $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$ while bidentate ligands viz. 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline (B) form compounds of composition $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot \text{B}$.

Stoichiometric composition of these addition compounds has been established by elemental analysis. The analytical data is given in Table 1. The molar conductance values of the millimolar solutions of the complexes in nitrobenzene are even lower than the parent complex, thus, suggesting them to behave as non-electrolytes. Molecular weight determination of some of these adducts in nitrobenzene where solubility permitted, suggest that they exist as monomers in this solvent.

nitrogen atoms of these ligands has been indicated by positive shifts in (C=C) and (C=N) ring stretching vibrations of the uncoordinated bases⁸ known to occur in the region 1590–1560 cm^{-1} by about 15–20 cm^{-1} . The (C-H) out of plane deformation modes around 759 cm^{-1} in case of 2,2'-bipyridyl has been found to split into two bands and is observed as a weak band around 766 cm^{-1} upon adduct formation. On the other hand, the infrared bands at 852 and 837 cm^{-1} due to out of plane (C-H) deformation vibration in 1,10-phenanthroline also appear to have moved to higher spectral regions on adduct formation suggesting coordination from both the nitrogens of the ligand⁹. The coordination from nitrogens of both 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline is further substantiated by the appearance of entirely new distinct bands around 290 cm^{-1} which have been assigned to $\nu(\text{Sn}\leftarrow\text{N})$ modes.

Table 1. Analytical data of complexes of $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ with nitrogenous bases

Complex	Colour and physical state	Experimental analysis of Sn	Molar conductance in PhNO_2	Molecular weight in PhNO_2
		(%) Found (Calcd.)	($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	Found (Calcd.)
$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{NH}$	Yellow solid	18.95 (18.85)	2.9	631 (631)
$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	Brown solid	17.86 (17.72)	2.7	652 (687)
$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot 2\text{py}$	Light green solid	18.42 (18.50)	1.5	643 (643)
$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot \text{bipy}$	Green solid	18.68 (18.50)	2.8	656 (656)
$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2 \cdot \text{phen}$	Brown solid	18.18 (18.14)	3.1	612 (641)

Additional evidence for the formation of these compounds has been inferred from IR spectra. Infrared spectra of the addition compounds of composition $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$ and $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{NH}$ have been quite helpful to throw some light on the structure of these compounds. The significant lowering of about 40–50 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{NH})$ mode observed in the region 3300–3400 cm^{-1} in pure amine has been attributed to the weakening of NH bond presumably due to the donation of the electrons from nitrogen to tin. This is further supported by lowering of $\nu(\text{C-N})$ stretching modes of Et_2NH and Et_3N observed in the region 1170–1190 and 1030–1230 cm^{-1} respectively by about 50–60 cm^{-1} in its adducts. The HNC deformation mode in Et_2NH has been found to undergo positive shifts in its adducts with $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$. These trends of shift in the $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{CN})$ and HNC deformation modes are in line with the earlier reports on the adducts of these bases with various transition metal halides⁷.

In case of addition compounds of $\text{Sn}(\text{dnp})_2$ with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline, coordination from both

Experimental

Materials :

Anhydrous stannous chloride (m.p. 244 °C) was obtained by treating the hydrated sample (30 g) with acetic anhydride as reported in literature¹⁰. Mercuric chloride (A.R.) was used as such without further purification. 2,4-Dinitrophenol was recrystallised from THF/ CHCl_3 before use. Sodium salt of 2,4-dinitrophenol was obtained as a yellow solid by the reaction of known amount of 2,4-dinitrophenol dissolved in absolute ethanol with equimolar amount of sodium hydroxide dissolved in the same solvent. The nitrogenous bases used in the present studies were of A.R. grade and used as such without further purification.

Preparation of tin(II) 2,4-dinitrophenoxide [$\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_2\text{-}2,4)_2$] : To the solution of SnCl_2 (1.0 g, 0.0052 mol) in dried tetrahydrofuran was added bimolar amount of 2,4-dinitrophenol (1.93 g, 0.0104 mol) and diethylamine (1.903 ml, 0.0104 mol) dissolved separately in the same solvent. An immediate colour change in the

reaction mixture solution, followed by the instantaneous separation of a white solid, identified as diethylamine hydrochloride from its melting point, was observed. The reaction mixture was stirred for 15–20 h at room temperature to ensure the completion of reaction. The white solid was removed by filtration under anhydrous condition. The filtrate thus obtained was concentrated and then left overnight. A greenish coloured solid separated out which was then repeatedly washed with petroleum ether and finely dried under vacuum. Yield : 86%.

Preparation of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_4]$: Double phenoxide of composition $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_4]$ was prepared by reacting a known amount of $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_2$ (1.0 g, 0.002 mol) suspended in methanol with bimolar amount of sodium 2,4-dinitrophenoxide (0.849 g, 0.004 mol) dissolved in the same solvent. The reaction contents were stirred at room temperature followed by boiling under reflux for about 1 h to ensure the completion of reaction. The resulting solution was concentrated followed by the addition of petroleum ether when a solid compound separated out. It was repeatedly washed with petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Preparation of $\text{Ni}[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_4]$: To methanolic solution of $\text{Na}_2[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_4]$ (0.75 g, 0.008 mol) was added equimolar amount of anhydrous NiCl_2 (0.108 g, 0.008 mol) dissolved in the same solvent. The reaction contents were first stirred at room temperature, followed by refluxing for about 5–6 h. Apart from a change in colour of solution, a white solid identified as NaCl separated out. It was removed from the solution by filtration. The filtrate was concentrated by distilling off the excess solvent, when a colored solid compound appeared. It was separated by filtration and dried under vacuum.

Reaction of tin(II) 2,4-dinitrophenoxide $[\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_2]$ with HgCl_2 : To a known amount of $\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_2$ (0.6 g, 0.0012 mol) in methanol was added bimolar amount of HgCl_2 (0.67 g, 0.0024 mol) dissolved in same solvent. The reaction mixture was first stirred for about 4–5 h followed by slight warming and was then refluxed to ensure the completion of reaction. A greyish solid compound later identified as mercurous chloride. Hg_2Cl_2 settled in the solution. This solid was separated by filtration and the solvent from the filtrate was distilled off to reduce to about one fourth of its original volume. The resulting solution was kept undisturbed overnight, when the coloured compound of composition $\text{SnCl}_2[(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4})_2]$ was obtained.

Preparation of addition compound $\text{Sn}[\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4}]_2$ with nitrogenous bases : To a known amount of $\text{Sn}[\text{OC}_6\text{H}_3(\text{NO}_2)_{2-2,4}]_2$ suspended in THF, was added bimolar amounts of pyridine, diethylamine and triethylamine and equimolar amounts of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl dissolved separately in the same solvent. An immediate colour change in the solution was observed. The reactants were stirred for about 6 h at room temperature and then refluxed for an hour to ensure the completion of the reaction. The resulting solution was then concentrated to about one fourth of its original volume when coloured compounds appeared as fine solids. In some cases, the compounds were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether. These compounds were separated by filtration, washed with petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Analysis and physical measurements : Tin in these compounds is determined as SnO_2 . The IR spectra ($4000\text{--}200\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded as KBr pellet using Nicolet-Avatar 1000 FTIR spectrometer. Proton NMR spectra was recorded on JEOL-PMX-6051 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard and CDCl_3 as solvent. Molecular weight determination of some of the adducts were carried out cryoscopically in nitrobenzene using a Beckmann thermometer while conductance measurements in the same solvent were made on an Elico-conductivity bridge (CM TYPE 82T) using 10^{-3} solution at 25°C . Thermograms (TGA/DTA curves) of complexes were recorded on simultaneous DT-TG Shimadzu Thermal Analyser DT-40 instrument. The analytical constants were : heating rate : $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$, sample size : 5–10 mg, platinum crucibles, reference : Al_2O_3 thermocouple : Pt/Pt-Rh 10%. Potentiometric titration of tin(II) 2,4-dinitrophenoxide vs HgCl_2 was carried out using Toshniwal potentiometer. Cyclic voltammetry has been carried out using EDCA-001 basic electrochemical system.

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